

AN OUTLINE OF INTERCONTINENTAL TRANSFER PRICING AND STATUTORY LAW

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ABSTRACT

Multinational Corporations have seen transfer pricing as a handy tool to achieving their acceptable corporate objectives to the detriment of home/host countries through unethical movement of one country's tax revenue to another, thus, making transfer pricing a top-of-mind concern for most Countries. In an attempt to fight perceived income shifting by Multinational Corporations (MNCs), some countries have enacted transfer pricing rules which are either in accordance with the widely adopted Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Transfer Pricing Guidelines or far from it. This paper therefore seeks to discuss the common transfer pricing methods employed by multinational corporations and the use of appropriate legislations in some selected countries to control the unwholesome transfer pricing strategies employed by MNCs.

Keywords: Transfer Pricing, Multinational Corporations (MNCs), Arm's – Length Principle.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

According to the International Labour Organization (as cited in Akhidime, 2011), Multinational Corporation is defined as a corporation that has its management headquarter in one country (home country) and operates in several other countries (host countries). Thus MNCs have features of cross-border operational activities carried out in two or more countries. Globalization and economic growth have driven the level of inter-company transactions to new heights. It is estimated that more than 2/3 of all business transactions worldwide take place within multinational corporations, a figure that is likely to grow further in the future (World Bank, 2011). Sequel to this, Transfer pricing has become a tool of analysis that reflects the determination of profits of these corporations and their subsidiaries. In International Taxation, transfer pricing is an issue which has continued to affect both the tax payer and the tax authorities. While transfer pricing is a valid business practice for associated companies in the pricing of inter-related sales within a corporation, it creates a suspicion for the tax authorities that the transfer price may be a form of shifting profit by MNCs with the intention of avoiding tax. Potential transfer pricing abuse is a particular

concern for developing countries, this is because of the sophistication of the foreign taxpayers and significant amount of money involve. Thus, developing nations like their developed counterpart, want to retain as much of the profit derived from the exploitation of their resources and other businesses carried out within their boundaries as much as possible, hence the need for local transfer pricing legislations by individual country.

2.0 INTERNATIONAL TRANSFER PRINCING

According to Dogan (as cited in Dogan, Deran, & Koksall, 2013), transfer pricing is defined as the price charged for the transfer of goods or services, tangible and intangible assets of a corporation raw materials, know-how and technology to its subsidiaries or branches. On his part, Akhidime (2011) described transfer pricing as a practice that reflects the price of goods and services or intangible transfers between a parent company and its subsidiaries, or as an alternative, the determination of profits of divisions within the same enterprise.

As a working definition, transfer pricing refers to the setting of price at which goods and services (tangibles and intangibles) are sold between related business entities in the same enterprise. For instance, if a parent company sells goods to a subsidiary company, the cost of those goods is referred to as the transfer price. Hence, a transfer price is “a price agreed upon between two decentralized profit-centre divisions for selling and buying a product, or a service, or a component.” (Ezejelue, 2008, p.439).

Therefore, International Transfer Pricing refers to the setting/determination of price at which goods and services are sold between a parent company and its foreign affiliates (subsidiaries).

2.1 OBJECTIVES OF INTERNATIONAL TRANSFER PRICING

The need for transfer pricing arises when goods or services (intangibles) are exchanged between organizational units of the same company. For instance, transfer pricing arises when one subsidiary of a corporation transfers inventory to another subsidiary of the same corporation, or when the parent company charges a subsidiary for administrative services, interest on corporate-wide financing, or royalties for intangible rights (Choi & Meek, 2011, p.448).

According to data published by the United Nations (UN) Conference on Trade and Development, nearly 70% of all international trade takes place between related parties. This has made transfer pricing to be on the radar in both developed and developing nations alike (Oyedele, Curtis, Sweigart, & Smallwood, 2013). However, the international transfer pricing policy by any corporation is influenced by the following key objectives.

i. Cost/Income Tax Minimization

Cost minimization and by extension profit maximization are common and important corporate objectives. The profits of these corporations involved in intercompany transactions are directly affected by transfer pricing. Therefore, manipulating transfer prices between countries is one way in which Multinational Corporations (MNCs) tend to achieve cost minimization and this is done through the shifting of profits from a higher tax rate jurisdiction to a lower tax rate jurisdiction by setting high transfer prices.

By way of illustration, Blu Jeans-Hong Kong, which is a wholly owned manufacturing ancillary of Global Enterprises (USA), that ships 500,000 pairs of designer blue jeans . They

cost Blu Jeans-Hong Kong for \$4.20 per pair as manufacturing cost. They assume that each garment wholesales for \$12 in the U.S., consolidated profits (after eliminating intercompany sales and costs) and taxes would total \$1,309,000 and \$591,000, respectively. This scenario is shown in Figure 1 below. Given a U.S. corporate tax rate of 35% versus 16.5% in Hong Kong, an increase in the transfer price of blue jeans would increase from \$6 to \$8 per pair to total after-tax income as shown in Figure 2.

In this same illustration, increasing the transfer price charged by the Hong Kong affiliate increases the taxable income in Hong Kong and reduces taxable income particularly for the U.S. affiliate by \$1,000,000. This is because the corporate tax rate is lower in Hong Kong than in the United States, corporate income taxes for the system as a whole decreased by \$185,000, with a corresponding increase in the consolidated after-tax earnings.

Figure 1: Tax Effects of Transfer Pricing

	Blu Jeans-HK	Blu Jeans-USA	Global Enterprises
Sales	\$3,000,000 ^a	\$6,000,000	\$6,000,000
Cost of sales	2,100,000	3,000,000 ^a	2,100,000
Gross Margin	\$ 900,000	\$ 3,000,000	\$ 3,900,000
Operating Expenses	500,000	1,500,000	2,000,000
Pre-tax income	\$ 400,000	\$ 1,500,000	\$ 1,900,000
Income tax (16.5%/35%) ^b	66,000	525,000	591,000
Net income	\$ 334,000	\$ 975,000	\$ 1,309,000

NOTE: ^a Based on a transfer price of \$6 per unit.

^b Income tax rates: Hong Kong 16.5%, United States 35%

Figure 2: Tax Effects of a Change in Transfer Prices

	Blu Jeans-HK	Blu Jeans-USA	Global Enterprises
Sales	\$4,000,000 ^a	\$6,000,000	\$6,000,000
Cost of sales	2,100,000	4,000,000 ^a	2,100,000
Gross Margin	\$1,900,000	\$ 2,000,000	\$ 3,900,000
Operating Expenses	500,000	1,500,000	2,000,000
Pretax income	\$1,400,000	\$ 500,000	\$ 1,900,000
Income tax (16.5%/35%) ^b	231,000	175,000	406,000
Net income	\$ 1,169,000	\$ 325,000	\$ 1,494,000

NOTE: ^a Based on a transfer price of \$8 per unit.

(Adapted from Choi & Meek, 2011, pp.448-449)

ii. Minimization of Worldwide Import Duties

Transfer prices can be used to reduce tariffs as import duties are usually applied to intra-company transfers as well as to sales made to unaffiliated buyers. For example, a company exporting goods to a subsidiary domiciled in a high-tariff country can reduce the tariff assessment by lowering the prices of goods sent there. Also, lowering transfer prices would

have been used to guard an existing process from the effects of increased foreign competition in the local market or another market; thus the profits earned in one country could subsidize the operation of another market.

iii. Avoidance of Financial Restrictions

Transfer pricing can be a handy tool for mitigating the impact of foreign government restrictions on the operations of a Multinational Corporation. For instance, where there is restriction by a country as to the amount of cash that may leave her boundaries (in the form of dividend payments), setting a high transfer price on goods imported into the country may enable the desired movement of cash since the importing subsidiary/division must remit payment.

Also, in order to manipulate profitability figures to their advantage, Multinational Corporations can use international transfer pricing. Thus, a multinational corporation that desires to show a lower profitability in its financial report can apply high transfer prices on imports to subsidiaries and vice versa.

iv. Managing Currency Fluctuations

When a country decides to devalue its national currency as a result of balance of payments problems (often resulting from an inflationary environment), multinational corporations may suffer a loss. However, losses from such devaluation may be avoided by an MNC through the use of inflated transfer prices to move funds from that country to some other affiliates in a foreign country.

2.2 TRANSFER PRICING METHODS

The attention towards transfer pricing is increasing worldwide. Thus, the issue justifies its significance when we recognize that transfer pricing i) is conducted on a relatively larger scale internationally than domestically; ii) is affected by more variables than are found in a strictly domestic setting; iii) varies from company to company, or country to country; iv) affects social economic and political relationships in MNCs. Thus, ascertaining how transfer prices are established among related companies is of paramount importance.

According to Ezejelue (2008: p.440) companies usually use the following transfer pricing methods:

1. Established market-based transfer prices;
2. Cost –based transfer prices;
3. Cost plus an allowed profit margin; and
4. Negotiated transfer prices.

1. Market-based Transfer Prices

This method involves transferring goods and services between related companies using the price at which such goods or services will be sold to an independent company or a third party. In other words, this approach to transfer pricing is used where the management policy grants autonomy to the buying and selling divisions to buy or sell the goods or services internally or externally (Okoye, 2011). Thus, the prevailing market price becomes the bases

for negotiation between the buying and selling divisions. The main advantage of this method is that it serves as an incentive for the producing division to control its costs so as to sell at competitive market price. Other advantages of this method include:

- a) It shows the opportunity cost to the transferring entity of not selling on the external market.
- b) It encourages the efficient use of the firm's source resources.
- c) Market –base transfer prices help to differentiate profitable from unprofitable operations.
- d) They are easier to define to taxing authorities as arm's – length prices.

However, the market-base transfer prices method has its own shortcomings, some of which include:

- a) Using market-price does not give a firm much room to adjust prices for competitive or strategic purposes.
- b) There is often no intermediate market for the product of service in question, since MNCs engage in transactions that independent enterprises do not undertake e.g. transfer of valuable, closely held technology to subsidiary.

2. Cost-based Transfer Price

This method involves a multinational corporation transferring goods or services to a subsidiary on the basis of the production cost, with no element of profit. This method has to its advantage the following: It is simple to use, it is determined based on readily available data, it is easy to justify to tax authorities, and it is easily routinized, thus helping to avoid internal frictions that often accompany more arbitrary systems.

However, the cost-base transfer pricing method is not flawless. Thus,

- a) The sale of goods or services at actual cost may provide little incentive for sellers to control their costs.
- b) This method overemphasizes historical costs, which ignore competitive demand- and also supply relationships, It does not allocate costs to scrupulous products or services in a satisfactory manner.

3. Cost-plus Transfer Price

When transfers are made at actual cost of production, the buying division takes all the gains from trade, leaving the supplying firm with nothing. To overcome this problem, the supplying firm is allowed to add a mark-up in order to make a “rational” profit. The transfer price must be viewed as an estimated market price.

4. Negotiated Transfer Price

According to Okoye (2011), under this method, the divisional managers have come together and have bargained for the price that will be paid by the purchasing department. Every divisional manager usually bargains to get a trade advantage for his division. Usually, top-management intervenes during such negotiation by providing guidelines which will benefit the entire organization. Such guidelines are necessary to prevent very hard bargaining between divisional managers which might create unfriendly relationship between them.

2.2.1 Policy Guidelines on Transfer Pricing

It is usually necessary for top management of an organization to have a clear policy on transfer pricing matters that fits the peculiar situation of the organization and the level of autonomy to be granted to the divisional managers (Okoye, 2011). These policy guidelines are designed to enable the organization achieve its corporate goals and prevent responsibility centre managers from pursuing their divisional objectives in preference to corporate interest.

However, these policy guidelines may vary but all divisional managers must understand without ambiguity the policies that affect them specifically. Issues in the policy statement may include:

- i. Intra-factory sales must be accepted by both buying and selling divisions whenever the situation arises. For instance, Division X has no right to deny Division Y supply of vital parts for production simply because an outside company offered it higher prices for the parts.
- ii. Where transfer price is between two profit centre divisions, the policy may fix 12% of standard or budgeted cost of production as the market price.
- iii. An ad hoc committee must be in place to ensure that transfer price policies are fully complied with by all divisions involved.

2.3 ACTIVITIES OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN THE FIELD OF TRANSFER PRICING

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the United Nations have been in the forefront in setting standards for international transfer pricing (Ezejelue, 2008). Their primary motive was to provide necessary guidelines that will assist the tax authorities and the tax payers in establishing an appropriate allocation of income and expenses between related parties in different countries in order to minimize tax conflicts. However, a summary of the activities of these organizations is as shown below:

a) Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

The OECD is an international economic organization founded in 1961 with the primary aim of stimulating economic progress and world trade. It is made up of 34 countries, most of which are developed countries. Examples of OECD member countries include Australia, Canada, Denmark, France, Hungary, Israel, Korea, Portugal, Sweden, United Kingdom, Japan, United States, Chile, Greece, Italy, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Turkey, Iceland, etc. The OECD has its headquarters at the Chateau de la Muette in Paris, France.

For about five decades, the OECD has continued to develop internationally accepted transfer pricing rules targeted at governing the ways its member and non-member countries tax profits which arise from related parties' transactions. The OECD has been able to achieve this through the publication of the OECD model tax convention which is geared towards the elimination of international double taxation as well as aiding the tax authorities to minimize the increasing rate of tax evasion and avoidance by multinational corporations.

However, the members of the OECD agreed on common methods and practice in determining the true price of related parties' transactions, which are outlined in the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines. Precisely, the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines (2010) outline five methods of determining the arm's length nature of transfer prices. The arm's length principle is currently the widely accepted guiding principle in choosing an acceptable transfer price. Under this principle, transactions between commonly controlled companies are compared

with transactions between unrelated entities in order to determine an acceptable transfer price. Therefore, these methods include:

1. The Comparable Uncontrolled Price (CUP) method,
2. The Resale Price Method (RPM)
3. The Cost Plus Method (CPM)
4. The Transactional Net Margin Method (TNMM);
5. The Profit Split Method (PSM)

1. The Comparable Uncontrolled Price (CUP) Method

This method involves setting transfer prices by making reference to price used in comparable transaction between independent Corporations or between the corporations and an unrelated third party (Choi, & Meek, 2011). In order for this method to be applicable, characteristics of the transactions among related entities and the transactions among unrelated entities must be comparable. This is the most frequently used method by virtue of its characteristics of direct comparison.

2 The Resale Price Method: This method calculates an arm's length price starting with the final selling price which the item in question is sold to an unrelated third party. A suitable margin to cover costs and an ordinary profit is after deducted from this price in order to arrive at the intra-company transfer price. However, this method is typically used when the unit buying the item is a distributor or sales subsidiary.

3. The Cost-Plus Method: This is a work forward approach that involves adding a mark-up to the transferring affiliate's cost in local currency. The mark-up typically includes: the imputed financing costs related to export inventories, receivables, and assets employed; and a percentage of cost covering manufacturing, warehousing, distribution, internal shipping, and other costs which are related to export operations.

The method is essentially applied when semi-finished goods are transferred between foreign affiliates, or where one entity is a sub-contractor for another.

4. The Transactional Net Margin Method: Under this method, the net profit margin of a controlled taxpayer resulting from a non-arm's length controlled transactions and the net profit margin achieved by arm's length non-related parties from identical transactions are examined and compared.

5. The Profit Split Method: This method involves dividing the profit generated in a related party transaction between the affiliated companies in an arm's length transaction. This method is used when product or market benchmarks are not available.

b) The United Nations (UN)

The United Nations Model Double Taxation Convention involving developed and developing countries was produced by the United Nations in order to provide developing countries with a basis when negotiating and signing Double Taxation Agreements (DTAs) with developed countries. Also, the UN pursues the objective of assisting countries in their economic, social and environmental development through its Department of Economic and Social Affairs (DESA). Within the DESA, the Committee of Experts on International Cooperation in Tax Matters (UN Expert Committee) has been dedicated to working specifically on issues regarding transfer pricing and international cooperation among developing countries.

The UN Expert Committee in 2009 initiated its work on the UN Transfer Pricing Manual for Developing Countries (TP Manual) and published new working drafts on 31st May, 2011.

The TP Manual is designed that to responds to the particular needs of developing countries and tries offers a step-by-step approach to adopting and implementing transfer pricing legislation in developing countries. However, in its draft, the UN Expert Committee establishes a clear reference to existing guidelines and endorses the various element of the principles contained in the OECD transfer pricing guidelines (e.g. the Arm's length principle as emphasized in Article 9 of the UN Model Convention), (Pwc, 2012).

3.0 INTERNATIONAL TRANSFER PRICING LEGISLATIONS IN SELECTED COUNTRIES

Although the arm's length principle as recommended by the OECD guideline has be applied by virtually all OECD member countries and other non-member states, there still exists some discrepancies particularly in areas of international transfer pricing methods and penalties (Ezejelue, 2008). Below is a review of international transfer pricing legislations in some selected Countries.

i. United Kingdom

The law pertaining to transfer pricing in the United Kingdom originated from a regulation dated back in 1915, which was revised in 1951 and 1998. The Inland Revenue is the highest authority in relation to taxation in the UK. According to Achilles and Smith (as cited in Dogan et al., 2013) the legislation in schedule 28AA ICTA 1988 commits itself to interpreting transfer pricing transactions in accordance with the principles of the OECD guidelines.

As a member of the OECD, the five methods specified by the OECD in determining arm's length prices i.e. the CUP method, cost plus method, Resale price method, the profit split method and transactional net margin method are generally recognized and applied in the UK. Also, according to the UK regulations, a penalty situation arises if there is an inaccuracy in the documents provided by an enterprise. The UK transfer pricing regulations spelt out the penalties for potential lost revenue arising from inaccuracies as follows:

- a) If the inaccuracy is due to carelessness, 30% of potential lost revenue;
- b) If the inaccuracy is deliberate and not concealed, 70% of potential lost revenue;
- c) If the inaccuracy is deliberate and concealed, 100% of potential lost revenue.

ii. Australia

Australia is an OECD member and has a representative on the OECD Transfer Pricing Task Force. Australia's transfer pricing legislation was introduced on 27th May 1981. Since then, the Australian Taxation Office (ATO) has issued a series of major rulings and publications providing guidance in applying the legislation. And these legislations are been reviewed. The ATO is dedicated towards enhancing taxpayers' compliance with Australia's transfer pricing rules and continues to work closely with authorities in other jurisdiction and international bodies in order to minimize double taxation, resolve transfer pricing disputes and share vital information (Pwc, 2012)

And as a member of the OECD, the Australian Taxation Office generally followed the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines as contained in the Australia's tax rulings, although it is not under the obligation to follow them when applying Division 13. Division 13 of part III of the income Tax Assessment Act 1936 contains Australia's domestic law dealing with transfer pricing. It is considered as an anti-avoidance division which aimed at counteracting international profit-shifting techniques by multinational corporations.

In cases of transfer pricing adjustments, the Australian transfer pricing rules provided strict penalties ranging from 10% to 50% of the additional tax as contained in the Taxation Ruling TR98/16 depending on the circumstances/motive behind the adjustment.

Finally, a formal Advance Pricing Arrangements (APAs) is available in Australia. APAs are mechanism whereby a MNC and a taxing authority voluntarily negotiate an agreed transfer pricing methodology that is binding on both parties for tax purposes.

iii. United States

In the United States, the arm's length standard has been used to determine whether cross-border, inter-company transfer pricing produces a clear reflection of income for US Federal income tax purposes since 1934. In 1986, the Inland Revenue Service (IRS) issued regulations in Section 482 of the Internal Revenue Code that provided procedural rules for applying the arm's – length standard and specific pricing methods for testing the arm's length character of transfer pricing results. As a member of the OECD, the OECD Guidelines are a significant point of reference for many of the US major trading partners in dealing with transfer pricing issues. However, there still exist some discrepancies between the US transfer pricing regulations and the OECD Guidelines. For instance in the US, the Comparable Profit method (CPM) is in practice becoming population due to the availability of sufficient data to implement it, despite the disqualification of the CPM by the OECD and its rejection by many other countries (Ezejelue, 2008). Also, over the years the US has developed some complex rules, such as the Advance Pricing Agreements (APAs) introduced in March, 1991; the rules on tangibles and intangibles in July 1994, the rules on cost sharing developed in December, 1995 and reviewed in December 2011; the rules as well as attached penalties with respect to documentation by the taxpayer were also developed in February 1996.

In addition to the above, the US transfer pricing regulations also introduced the 'Best Method Rule' were a taxpayer must select one of the transfer pricing methods that yields the most accurate or best result to test the arm's length character of its transfer prices. In other words, the Best method rule requires the Taxpayer to select the best transfer pricing method based on the facts and circumstances of the case.

Finally, in the U.S, severe penalties are imposed on valuation misstatements in connection with Section 482 adjustments. Penalties may be up to 40% of the additional taxes that result from income adjustments.

iv. Nigeria

Issues of inter-company or related parties' transactions have been incorporated into the Nigeria legislations for many years. Specifically, Section 17 of the Personal Income Tax Act (PITA) 2004, Section 22 of the Companies Income Tax Act (CITA) 2004, and Section 15 of the Petroleum Profit Tax Act (PPTA) 2004 all made provisions for the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) to make adjustment on inter-company transactions which are deemed to produce artificial result reducing taxable income in Nigeria. However, prior to 2012, these rules were more or less paper work, because there was no framework for their enforcement.

Furthermore, Nigeria over the years has been working to develop her own transfer pricing rules in accordance with the OECD guidance. And in May 2012, the FIRS released a draft of the transfer pricing rules which was later finalized in August 2012 as the Income Tax

(Transfer Pricing) Regulations No.1, 2012 (Oyedele et al., 2013). This Act shall be referred to as the ‘Regulation’.

Though Nigeria is not a member of the OECD, her transfer pricing rules are in compliance with the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines. Specifically, the Income Tax (Transfer pricing) Regulations adopted the five primary methods specified in the OECD Guidelines in determining an acceptable transfer price and any other method which may be prescribed by regulations made by the FIRS from time to time. Also, the Advance Pricing Agreements (APAs) is also available in Nigeria’s transfer pricing regulations. The Regulations specifically states that the APAs between the FIRS and Connected Taxable Persons (CTPs) will have a term of three years unless cancelled under certain circumstance by either the FIRS or the CTPS or both.

In terms of documentation, the Regulations require taxpayer to prepare transfer pricing documents before the due date for filing the income tax liability for the year in which the documented transactions occurred (Section 6). Finally, in relation to offences arising from understatement of tax or improper use of transfer prices, the Regulations did not provide a unique penalty for offenders, rather, it relied on the existing tax Acts in the Nation.

v. Brazil

The Brazilian Transfer pricing rules took effect from 1st January 1997. And since then, they have been very controversial. Contrary to the OECD guideline, UN Model Convention and the transfer pricing rules introduced by some of Brazil’s key Latin American trading partners like Argentina and Mexico, Brazil’s transfer pricing rules do not adopt the internationally accepted arm’s length principle. Rather, Brazil’s transfer pricing rules define maximum price ceiling for deductible expenses on inter-company import transactions and minimum gross income floors for inter-company export transactions. The rules addressed import and export of products, service and rights charged between related parties. The Brazilian transfer pricing rules characterised foreign persons as being related when both are located in low tax jurisdiction whether or not a relationship exists between them. Thus, the transfer pricing rules do not apply to two Brazilian sister companies, leaving the possibility for multinational corporations to conduct inter-company transfers between their Brazilian subsidiaries on non-arm’s length terms. Also, a foreign company and a Brazilian company may be considered to be related if the foreign company owns as little as 10% of the Brazilian company or when the same person owns at least 10% of the capital of each.

Other material difference arises from globally adopted transfer pricing regimes which include the Brazilian transfer pricing legislation’s exclusion of a best method or most appropriate method rule; accordingly , a tax payer may choose the respective pricing method.

In the case of transfer pricing offences, if the Brazilian tax authorities were to conclude that there is deficiency and make an income adjustment, penalties may be imposed at the rate of 75% of the assessed tax deficiency. The rate may be reduced by 50% of the penalty imposed if the taxpayer agrees to pay the assessed tax deficiency within 30 days without contesting assessment.

3.1 CHALLENGES OF TRANSFER PRICING IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

For many developing countries, equipping an administration to deal fairly and effectively with transfer pricing issues seems to be a very difficult task. Some of the challenges faced by these developing countries in dealing effectively with issues of transfer pricing include:

1 **Lack of Comparables:** Comparative pricing is one of the foundations of the arm's length principle. In practice, proper comparability is often found to be difficult and this to many weakens the continued validity of the arm's length principle; since the traditional transfer pricing methods (i.e. CUP, Resale price and cost plus) rely directly on comparables. Applying the arm's length principle can be very difficult in developing countries because there tend to be fewer organized players in such sector than in developed countries; and the comparable information may be incomplete

2 **Lack of Knowledge and Requisite Skills:** Transfer pricing methods are complex and time-consuming, often requiring time and attention from some of the most skilled and valuable human resources in both multinational corporations and tax authorities. This kind of complexity and knowledge requirement puts tremendous strain on both the taxpayers and tax authorities, especially in developing countries where there tend to be scarce resources and non-availability of appropriate training.

3 **Complexity of Rules:** Rules based on the arm's length principle are becoming increasingly difficult and complex to administer. Today, transfer pricing compliance typically involves large and expensive database and high level expertise to handle. This might not be available in developing countries. In the same vein, tax authorities of many developing countries do not have sufficient resources to examine the facts and circumstances of every case in order to ascertain the acceptable transfer price, especially in cases where is lack of comparable.

4.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Multinational Corporations employ international transfer pricing to justifiably meet core international business objectives that include worldwide cost /income tax and import duties minimization, avoidance of financial restrictions, managing currency fluctuation etc. However, the Tax Authorities of some countries have embraced the arm's length principle as provided by the OECD Transfer Pricing Guidelines in ascertaining an acceptable transfer price in order to minimize the high level of tax avoidance /evasion by most multinational corporations.

Though some countries across the globe have made local provisions in dealing with transfer pricing issues, there is still much to be done. More administrative infrastructure should be put in place to ensure full compliance. The Tax Authorities of developing country like Nigeria need to upgrade their database in order to keep in pace with the fast increasing globalization, and specific strict penalties should be promulgated in order to deter Multinational Corporations from engaging in transfer pricing manipulations.

REFERENCES

- Akhidime, A. E. (2011). International transfer pricing regulation: Nigeria experience. *JORIND* (9), 350-357.
- Choi, F.D., & Meek, G.K. (2011). *International Accounting* (7th ed.). Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Companies Income Tax Act, 2004.

- Dogan, Z., Deran, A., & Koksai, A.G. (2013). Factors influencing the selection of methods and determination of transfer pricing in multinational companies: A case study of United Kingdom. *International Journal of economic and financial issues*, 3 (3), 734-742.
- Ezejelue, A.C. (2008). *A primer on International accounting*. Uturu, Abia State: Clearprint Publishing.
- Income Tax (Transfer Pricing). Regulations No.1, 2012. Retrieved from <http://www.firs.gov.ng/Tax-management/Tax Forms Documents/TP Regulation.pdf>.
- Okoye, A. E. (2011). *Cost Accountancy: Management Operational Applications (2nd Edition)*. Benin City: Mindex Publishing.
- Oyedele, T., Curtis, A., Sweigart, E., & Smallwood, R. (2013). The impact of Nigeria new transfer pricing rules on multinational enterprises. *LexisNexis Emerging Issues Analysis* (6959).
- Personal Income Tax Act (as amended), 2011.
- Petroleum Profit Tax Act, 2004.
- PwC (2012). International transfer pricing 2013/14. Retrieved from <http://www.pwc.com/internationaltp>
- PwC (n.d). Transfer pricing and developing countries; Final report. Retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/resources/documents/common/publications/studies/transfer_pricing_dev_countries.pdf
- UN Tax Committee (2011). An introduction to transfer pricing: A working draft. Retrieved from http://www.un.org/esa/ffd/wp-content/uploads/2011/06/20110607_TP_Chapter_1_Introduction.pdf
- World Bank (2011). “Transfer Pricing Technical Assistance Global Tax Simplification Programme”. Presentation given by Rajul Awasthi in Brussels, 24 February, 2011.